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Protection Scheme Aftermath of the New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants in United Kingdom

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Abstract: This research explores the United Kingdom (UK) stance on asylum and migrant protection in light of the principles outlined in the New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants. This Declaration, being a global agreement, led to the establishment of two key global compacts in 2018, guiding nations on migration governance. UK emphasizes its tradition of offering asylum to those escaping persecution, recent legislation has raised concerns. However, Nationality and Borders Act of 2022 introduces provisions that can discriminate against refugees based on their mode of arrival, even criminalizing asylum seekers. The 2023 Illegal Migration Act operates in the context of a significant asylum backlog, causing physical and psychological distress to individuals in the UK's asylum system. The UK's approach to offshore processing, exemplified by the UK-Rwanda agreement, raises concerns about circumventing international obligations and burden-sharing. The "Hostile Environment" policy disproportionately impacts people of color, potentially discouraging access to essential services. UK's approach to asylum and migrant protection needs reassessment to align with international standards. Revisiting recent legislation, addressing the asylum backlog, and reconsidering offshore agreements are crucial. Upholding modern slavery protections and reiterating the commitment to providing refuge while maintaining a compassionate approach is essential for the UK to fulfill its global responsibilities outlined in the New York Declaration.

Keywords: refugees; New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants; Brexit; asylum; protection; legal obligations

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1. Introduction

The New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants¹ (the New York Declaration) being a UN declaration was adopted in 2016 to express global solidarity and protection of refugees (Triggs et al. 2020). This declaration aims to address the issues associated with migration assisting states achieve their human rights duties while managing migration. The promises included in the statement approved by the member states demonstrate that protecting individuals forced to leave their homes and helping the countries that are hosting them is a communal obligation. This duty needs to be performed in a way that is more equal and consistent.

UK being a United Nations (UN) member, has to respect international agreements and norms associated with the protection of migrants and refugees. The internal laws, policies, and international obligations all contribute to the country's approach to safeguard migrants and asylum seekers. UK offers refuge, housing, and financial assistance to asylum seekers while their claims are being processed.² These efforts are in line with the general goals of the global instruments, meant to secure the health and safety of persons who are seeking protection.

2. Methods

This article follows the qualitative research methodology to gather information from both primary and secondary sources for multi-dimensional information. Primary and Secondary

¹ Available online: <https://www.unhcr.org/what-we-do/protect-human-rights/asylum-and-migration/new-york-declaration-refugees-and-migrants> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

² Available online: <https://righttoremain.org.uk/toolkit/asylum-support/#:~:text=This%20is%20provided%20by%20the.for%20asylum%20has%20been%20refused> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

materials, such as textbooks, case reference, academic publications, legal journals, media and newspaper reports, conference papers, official documents, and internet sources were used in this research.

3. UK role in Protecting Asylum Seekers and Migrants

Previously, UK has been a haven for those who are in need. Based on the UN 1951 Refugee Convention³, also known as Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees or the Geneva Convention of 28 July 1951 to which UK is a party, the legal framework for the protection of refugees is established (Micinski 2023). UK being a party to international human rights accords, has to respect the rights of all persons who are present inside its boundaries, regardless of whether or not they possess a valid immigration status. Asylum seekers and migrants are protected by this commitment, including the protection of their rights.

A total of 89.3 million individuals were forcefully relocated around the globe by the end of the year 2021.⁴ Turkey with Syrian refugees is the top country hosting refugees for the eighth year in a row (Nanda 2017). During the year 2021, Europe issued judgments about 548,000 asylum requests, and refugee status or some other type of protection was granted to approximately 41% of these requests.⁵ The people from Syria Iran, Eritrea, Syria, and Sudan were the most prominent given asylum in the UK.⁶ UK provides humanitarian aid and assistance to refugees and migrants affected by crises around the world. In 2021, the UK had approximately 56,500 individuals applying for asylum, ranking it as the fourth highest in comparison to the EU+ (comprising the EU-27, Switzerland, Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway).⁷ During the same year, the UK offered asylum or some other type of protection to about 13,000 individuals (at the initial decision stage, not including appeals), positioning it the sixth in the ranking.⁸ In 2021 and 2022, around 21,400 Afghans were relocated to the UK in advance and during the withdrawal of UK forces from Afghanistan.⁹ In 2024, around 210,000 Ukrainians came to the UK (as of November) under two new routes created for individuals escaping the conflict.¹⁰ During the Ukraine crisis, UK provided visa support for Ukrainian nationals who were unable to return to Ukraine when their existing visa expired. This allowed them to extend their stay in the UK without having to leave and reapply from overseas. Ukrainian refugees already in the UK were also able to claim asylum.¹¹

4. Protection Mechanism under New York Declaration in the Light of Global Compact

The two global instruments associated with the New York Declaration are:

i. *The Global Compact on Refugees (GCR)*

GCR was adopted in December 17, 2018 by the UN General Assembly and addresses the worldwide refugee crisis with a comprehensive and fair approach to refugee response. It guarantees protection, safety, and vital services to refugees while focusing on long-term solutions and burden-sharing among nations. GCR seeks to eliminate humanitarian crises enhancing the quality of life for refugees and the communities hosting them.¹² The four primary goals of GCR include alleviating the burdens on host nations, boosting the independence of refugees, increasing opportunities for resettlement in other countries and contributing to the establishment of safe and respectable circumstances for refugees to return to their places of origin.¹³

ii. *The Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration (GCM)*

Adopted in December 2018, GCM14 address concerns associated with migration across international borders providing a cooperative framework for managing migration in a safe and orderly way while respecting the rights and dignity of migrants. Being a UN agreement, GCM emphasizes the importance of reducing irregular migration, enhancing legal pathways for migration, and addressing the root causes of migration. It promotes international cooperation and coordination on migration-related issues.

4.1 UK Protection scheme under Global Compact on Refugees and Migration

i. *Burden Sharing*

Under the New York Declaration, the global compact on refugees emphasizes sharing the responsibility for hosting and assisting refugees. The UK government has committed to spend a portion of its gross national income (GNI) for assistance. This includes funding for humanitarian and development programs that benefit countries hosting refugees. Official development assistance (ODA) funds are used to support basic services such as healthcare, education, and shelter for both refugees and host communities (Martin et al.2017).

³ Available online: <https://www.unhcr.org/about-unhcr/overview/1951-refugee-convention> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

⁴ Available online: <https://www.refugeecouncil.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/The-UKS-role-in-the-international-refugee-protection-systemJuly-2022.pdf> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

⁵ Statistical information on outcomes of asylum appeals and court proceedings is under-reported in UNHCR statistics, particularly in developed countries, because this type of data is often either not collected by States or not published separately

⁶ Available online: <https://hansard.parliament.uk/Lords/2023-01-24/debates/4C58C4CC-23F9-415D-B840-7C24C7F4A38B/AsylumSeekersSyriaAfghanistanEritreaIranAndSudan> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

⁷ Available online: <https://www.unhcr.org/uk/asylum-uk> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

⁸ Ibid,5

⁹ Available online: <https://migrationobservatory.ox.ac.uk/resources/briefings/afghan-asylum-seekers-and-refugees-in-the-uk/> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

¹⁰ Available online: <https://migrationobservatory.ox.ac.uk/resources/briefings/ukrainian-migration-to-the-uk/> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

¹¹ Available online: <https://www.redcross.org.uk/get-help/get-help-as-a-refugee/help-for-refugees-from-ukraine> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

¹² Available online: <https://globalcompactrefugees.org/about-digital-platform/global-compact-refugees> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

¹³ Ibid, 4

¹⁴ Available online: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Global_Compact_for_Migration (accessed on 8 February 2025)

UK is a key donor for the Syrian crisis. From February 2012 to December 2024, it allocated over £235 million to address the immediate needs of vulnerable individuals within Syria and refugees in the surrounding region.¹⁵ This support also extended to countries hosting refugees from Syria.¹⁶ UK supported a \$246 million loan to expand Lebanon's National Poverty Targeting Programme.¹⁷ However, the ODA policy led to temporarily reduce its ODA spending from 0.7% of gross national income (GNI) to 0.5% of GNI.¹⁸ This has led to concerns about the impact on the most vulnerable populations in the world, as they rely on UK-funded programs for their basic needs. UK's aid budget for Lebanon significantly decreased by 88% from 2019–20 to 2021–24, directly impacting the refugee well-being and the effectiveness of humanitarian programs. It also reduced the UK's ability to negotiate greater refugee inclusion in national systems during a period of increasing poverty among refugees and host communities.¹⁹

ii. Refugee Rights Protection

GCR is a comprehensive framework designed to enhance the global response to refugee crises protecting the rights of refugees around the world. Many countries, including UK have signed international treaties and conventions that set legal duties for refugee rights and protection. The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR)²⁰ is incorporated into the legal system of the UK via the Human Rights Act of 1998²¹. Under ECHR, persons, including refugees and asylum seekers, can file claims in the courts of the UK. In UK after Brexit, the government will have an authority over its immigration and asylum policy (Pécoud,2021).

iii. Long-Term Solution

GCR encourages long-term solutions, particularly the integration of refugees into host communities. This approach is in line with the principles of sustainability and self-reliance for refugees. In the UK, refugee settlement and integration are already in place, which align with the objectives of the compact.

4.2 UK Resettlement schemes for refugees²²

The Community Sponsorship Scheme²³ program engages local communities, organizations that are part of civil society, and religious groups to provide direct assistance to refugee families in their areas. It is a useful addition to the UK Resettlement Scheme (UKRS)²⁴. The Afghan Relocation and Assistance Policy (ARAP)²⁵ was purposed to relocate former employees who were still working locally in Afghanistan and who are now facing significant challenges in changed regime. The Afghan Citizens' Resettlement Scheme (ACRS)²⁶ operational since 2022 is designed to resettle a maximum of 20,000 Afghans. There are three primary routes by which various groups of Afghan refugees might go. One of the worldwide initiatives known as the Mandate Resettlement Scheme²⁷ is designed to establish recognized refugees in the UK with members of their immediate family who are prepared to provide them with housing and assistance. A child, spouse, parent, or grandparent who is above the age of 65 is required to be a member of the family in the UK. Offering sanctuary and assistance to vulnerable groups, particularly those who have been afflicted by violence and persecution, is reflected in the programs that UK has established (Heath 2022). With the exception of the Afghan schemes, above schemes helped resettle 29,429 individuals to UK since 2014 and June 2024.²⁸ Approximately 148,000 individuals were awarded asylum or some permission to stay in UK during the same period.²⁹

5. Post-Brexit UK on Asylum and Migrants

Since 2021, UK will not be obliged to follow the Dublin framework, Eurodac, and other fundamental elements of the European Union's migration and refugee system (Micinski 2023). Asylum seekers, especially unaccompanied youngsters, who are attempting

¹⁵ Available online: https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/news-stories/news/eu-provides-eu235-million-humanitarian-aid-syrians-2025-01-17_en (accessed on 8 February 2025)

¹⁶ Availableonline: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm5803/cmselect/cmintdev/426/report.html#footnote-095-backlink> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

¹⁷ Available online: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2021/01/12/us246-million-to-support-poor-and-vulnerable-lebanese-households-and-build-up-the-social-safety-net-delivery-system> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

¹⁸ Available online: <https://odi.org/en/insights/lessons-from-the-uk-spending-review/> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

¹⁹ Available online: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm5803/cmselect/cmintdev/426/report.html#footnote-095-backlink> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²⁰ Available online: <https://www.echr.coe.int/european-convention-on-human-rights> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²¹ Available online: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1998/42/contents> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²² Available online: <https://www.london.gov.uk/programmes-strategies/communities-and-social-justice/migrants-and-refugees/helping-resettlement-refugees> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²³ Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/apply-for-full-community-sponsorship/community-sponsorship-guidance-for-prospective-sponsors> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²⁴ Available online: <https://northwestsmp.org.uk/refugee-resettlement/refugee-resettlement-programmes/uk-resettlement-scheme-ukrs/> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²⁵ Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/afghan-relocations-and-assistance-policy/afghan-relocations-and-assistance-policy-information-and-guidance> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²⁶ Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/afghan-citizens-resettlement-scheme> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²⁷ Available online: <https://unitedkingdom.iom.int/resettlement> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

²⁸ Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/afghan-citizens-resettlement-scheme> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

²⁹ Ibid,20

to reconcile with their family members residing in UK, are facing significant challenges.³⁰ When UK was a member of the EU, it used Dublin mechanism³¹, to return to other EU members to return persons who could provide evidence that they had been through several other European countries before arriving the UK. However, Brexit had made their entry to the UK easier via the English Channel in smaller boats. Since this pattern was first detected on a major scale in 2018, the number of people who crossed the Channel has been steadily increasing each year as shown in Figure 1(Taylor, 2021).

Figure 1. The total number of people recorded as having entered the UK in small boats.³²

The Illegal Migration Act³³ of 2023 intended prohibiting persons from using small boats to traverse the English Channel. This legislation would result in the asylum request of any individual who arrived UK in an unauthorized manner being labeled as "inadmissible". In such situations, the Home Office would not look into the individual's claim (Adijāne 2020). These persons may be subject to imprisonment for an unlimited period, followed by relocation to either their home country or, to a "safe third country."³⁴

Individuals may be deported to their home country or to another where they hold an identification card or passport. The act identifies 57 countries, eight of which are only for men, for deportation under two conditions: either it is the "safe third country" from which the departee arrived UK, or there is a "reason to believe that they will be admitted" to that country, possibly through an asylum transfer agreement (Donald and Gorgan 2024). Claims for asylum or protection of human rights made by persons residing in countries that are deemed to be "safe" in accordance with the act is declared inadmissible, meaning they are not acknowledged legitimate. The home secretary can legally authorize a person to remain in the country if there are concerns that it may otherwise breach the ECHR or if there are special circumstances.³⁵

The "Illegal Migration Act" is in direct opposition to the commitments of the UK to international human rights. The government's assertion that individuals will be dissuaded from seeking asylum to UK if they are aware that they could face detention and deportation to countries such as Rwanda or other destinations is the fundamental premise of the Act (Anapol 2023). UK has signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with the government of Rwanda to establish an asylum transfer scheme (Goddard 2023). It is still unclear how the "detain and remove" approach will be properly executed with Rwanda creating uncertainty surrounding the logistical issues that may arise in future with Rwanda (Sturridge et al. 2022). This Act significantly changed the asylum system in UK including the establishment of asylum reception centers, the implementation of offshore asylum processing facilities (Devine 2022), and distinctions in treatment, which are based on the manner in which an individual arrived the UK (Hennebry et al. 2023). Amendments to the statute included in the Act, authorizes the government to transfer persons to a third country for processing their asylum requests outside the UK territories. This practice of processing requests is devoid of acts. It has proven to be expensive and inefficient in Australia, inflicting damage on the emotional well-being of asylum seekers, leading to high rates of self-inflicted injuries and suicides.³⁶

³⁰ Available online: <https://www.epc.eu/en/Projects/Post-Brexit-EU-UK-cooperation-on-migration-and-asylum~481714> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

³¹ Available online: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/common-european-asylum-system/country-responsible-asylum-application-dublin-regulation_en (accessed on 12 January 2025)

³² Ibid,11

³³ Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/illegal-migration-bill> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

³⁴ Available online: <https://www.refugeecouncil.org.uk/information/what-is-the-illegal-migration-act/> (accessed on 12 January 2025)

³⁵ Ibid,16

³⁶ Ibid, 21

5.1 Bypassing the New York Declaration Commitments

i. Evasion of the Family Reunification

Family reunification is a key component of the New York Declaration, according to para 57-part III Commitments for migrants of the Declaration. The asylum system is divided into two tiers under Clause 10 of the Nationality and Borders Act of 2022 (NABA).³⁷ Group 1 will consist of individuals who have arrived the UK via a safe country and have made a prompt claim for asylum (Gauci 2018). This group will be comparable to the path that was taken before the implementation of the NABA. All other persons will be placed in the "Group 2" category, and if their claims are successful, they will be granted "temporary refugee permission" status instead of full refugee status. This status, makes it possible to remain legally in the UK for thirty months. After ten years of lawful residency, there is the potential of settling down permanently in the UK. Those who have been granted temporary refugee status may face further challenges when attempting to bring their family members to join them in the UK via the family reunion route.³⁸ UNCHR observed that the position of "Group 2" is incompatible with the Refugee Convention.³⁹

ii. Home Office Hostile Environment Policy

The Hostile Environment policy⁴⁰ of the UK is a set of government measures and policies implemented to deter and restrict the activities of undocumented migrants making it difficult for them to live and work in the UK (Cenker et al.2018). Persons of color have been disproportionately harmed by the hostile environment measures, according to the policies implemented by the Home Office (Gentleman, 2023). According to the equity effect assessment, Indian, Pakistani, Nigerian, and Bangladeshi origin persons were among the most affected.⁴¹ This study is the first official evaluation of the practices that led to the Windrush Scandal.⁴² During this episode, thousands of people who held valid residence in the UK had difficulties in obtaining jobs, housing, access to healthcare, financial systems, and travel.

Part II of the New York Declaration makes commitments that apply to both refugees and migrants, and para 32 emphasizes the importance of providing refugees and migrants with access to essential services, including healthcare and education. The Hostile Environment policy, with its checks on immigration status for healthcare and restrictions on access to certain services, may discourage individuals from seeking necessary medical care and education. This can potentially lead to violations of the right to health and education as outlined in the Declaration (Xanthaki 2022). The New York Declaration underscores the principle of non-discrimination,⁴³ emphasizing that refugees and migrants should not be subject to discrimination. The Hostile Environment policy has been criticized for discrimination and racial profiling, potentially infringing this principle.

iii. Criminalizing the Right to Seek Asylum

NABA, in its current form, will impose unjustifiable penalties on most refugees seeking asylum in the country. This legislation introduces an asylum system that contradicts established international refugee protection principles and practices. At the core of this Act is the establishment of a new, lower-status category for the majority of refugees, particularly those who arrive spontaneously (Afaq and Sirohi 2018). Under the Act, it will be a criminal offense for asylum-seekers who require entry clearance to enter the UK without it, with a maximum sentence of four years' imprisonment. Irregular arrivals will face stigmatization, being deemed as unworthy and unwelcome, and they will have an uncertain status for ten years. They will be allowed access to public funds if they are in a state of poverty, and family reunion opportunities will be restricted.⁴⁴ The Declaration upholds the right to seek asylum in Para 67⁴⁵ commitment for refugees. The stringent immigration checks and deterrent measures of Hostile Environment policy and NABA, could potentially discourage individuals from asserting their demand and protection from UK.

6. Findings

The UK prides its long-standing legacy of being a friendly nation and record of providing refuge to those under persecution. NABA authorizes UK government to deport asylum seekers to places in which they have never set foot, to deport boats that are already at sea, and discriminate against refugees based on the manner in which they gained entry into the UK. One of the human rights is the freedom to seek refuge and granted. Asylum-seekers and refugees might be subject to penalties under the NABA, which

³⁷ Available online: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/id/ukpga/2022/36> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

³⁸ Ibid, 2

³⁹ Available online: <https://www.unhcr.org/uk/sites/uk/files/legacy-pdf/615ff04d4.pdf> (accessed on 8 February 2025)

⁴⁰ Available online: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Home_Office_hostile_environment_policy (accessed on 8 February 2025)

⁴¹ Ibid, 28

⁴² In 1948, the British Nationality Act conferred to citizens from the colonies the right to stay and pursue work in the United Kingdom. The British government need supplementary labor to mitigate post-World War II labor shortages and facilitate economic restoration. Concurrently, Caribbean countries had economic difficulties, whereas the employment vacancies in the UK presented an attractive prospect. Consequently, several arrivals assumed positions as manual laborers, drivers, cleaners, and nurses, so aiding in the formation of the National Health Service (NHS). The individuals who arrived in the UK until 1971 were known as the Windrush generation. In April 2018, it was disclosed that the UK Home Office had not preserved any records of persons given leave to stay and had failed to provide them with the requisite papers to confirm their legal status.

⁴³ Appendix II In pursuit of a worldwide compact for safe, orderly, and regular migration, II. Context, 5. We will engage in international cooperation to guarantee safe, orderly, and regular migration, with complete adherence to human rights and the humane treatment of migrants, irrespective of their migratory status. We emphasize the need of upholding the dignity of migrants and safeguarding their rights in accordance with relevant international law, especially the principle of non-discrimination.

⁴⁴ Ibid, 2

⁴⁵ We reaffirm respect for the institution of asylum and the right to seek asylum. We reaffirm also respect for and adherence to the fundamental principle of non-refoulement in accordance with international refugee law.

would be in violation of the principle of non-punishment in international law and international law since it would discriminate between different kinds of asylum applicants.

With an asylum "backlog," of thousands of pending petitions, the Illegal Migration Act, 2023, is proposed. This "backlog" makes people unclear about their position in the UK. The persistent presence inside the asylum system of the UK has had dramatic repercussions, including personal experiences of trauma, thoughts of self-harm, contact with hostility, and threats. These effects have been experienced on both a physical and psychological level. These repercussions are the result of spending years in a condition of uncertainty over asylum opportunities. The principles of the Refugee Convention are undermined when asylum-seekers are transferred to offshore destinations, which are often less developed. This strategy shifts the duties of the UK, establishing a precedent that is fraught with danger. If other countries start following this approach, it would lead to the bulk of asylum-seekers being sent to countries that have little resources and infrastructure to assist. One of the most divisive features of the Illegal Migration Act is the part declaring persons who enter the UK without legal permission unfit to get protections against modern slavery. The argument made by the government that asylum seekers have fraudulently claimed to be victims of modern slavery in order to avoid deportation is the driving force behind this.

7. Recommendations

Reviewing and changing the NABA will help to guarantee that it conforms with international human rights criteria. Clause 10 and clauses that can cause refugee prejudice depending on their means of entry should especially get specific consideration. UK should take swift and comprehensive action to address the asylum backlog. This should involve streamlining the asylum application process and ensuring that individuals do not endure prolonged uncertainty, which can have severe physical and psychological consequences. UK should review the policy of sending asylum-seekers to offshore sites, particularly less developed nations with regard to economy. This strategy should be changed to guarantee that refugees get sufficient help and protection because it might contravene the standards of the Refugee Convention. Maintaining modern slavery safeguards for every person regardless of their means of arrival into the UK is very vital. UK should keep a friendly and sympathetic attitude towards those applying for refuge.

8. Conclusions

Fundamental for world solidarity and the protection of refugees and migrants is the New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants. It lays the foundation for two important global compacts that guide countries in addressing migration challenges and maintaining human rights obligations. The UK-Rwanda agreement reveals its offshore processing approach, which raises questions about the avoidance of international commitments and fair burden-sharing. Work might be transferred to less developed nations benefiting from recent UK agreements in need of stronger infrastructure and resources. To guarantee adherence to international responsibilities, a comprehensive evaluation of refugee and migrant protection initiatives is absolutely required. For the UK, reevaluating offshore policy, looking at laws, and clearing backlog of asylum applications are all vital actions. The UK's New York Declaration depends on its capacity to maintain prohibitions against modern slavery and provide compassionate refuge.

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